

POWDER COATING OF CARBON FIBERS USING AQUEOUS FOAM

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ABSTRACT

A technique has been developed to continuously coat carbon fibers with polymer powders using an aqueous foam as a carrier medium. The polymer is slurried in a surfactant solution into which air is dispersed using a foam-generating device. The foam is applied to a moving carbon-fiber tow from a reservoir to control the amount of resin that is deposited on the fibers. The tow is then pulled through ovens where the foam is collapsed and the powder fused to the fibers. This process may be an attractive alternative to solution or slurry coating, where significant drying times are required, and to powder-coating in fluidized beds, where process control is often a problem.

This study involved using LaRC-TPI 1500 high flow powder dispersed in aqueous solutions of the nonionic surfactant Triton X-100. Preliminary experiments indicated that a relatively dry foam with a gas volume fraction greater than 97 percent was required for successful foam towpregging. Using a slurry concentration of 20 percent powder by weight, the minimum surfactant concentration needed to generate a stable foam in excess of 97 percent gas was 0.25 percent. Towpreg was fabricated successfully by doctoring powder-laden foam directly onto the moving tow. Two tubular ovens in series were used to collapse the foam and fuse the powder to the carbon fibers. Future work will include producing flexible towpreg that can be woven into fabric structures, and to incorporate the foam process into a multi-tow tape line to efficiently form prepreg using high-performance polymers.

KEY WORDS: Composites, Polymer Matrix; Polyimides; LaRC-TPI; Powder coating; Prepregging; Composite Processing

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1. INTRODUCTION

The task of combining high-performance polymer resins and reinforcing fibers to form composite materials is challenging. In the prepregging step, the polymer can be deposited on the fiber from the melt state, from solution, or in powder form from a slurry or a fluidized bed. The selection of a prepregging technique is dictated by a number of factors, including the softening temperature of the polymer, the melt viscosity of the polymer, the solubility of the resin in a "reasonable" solvent, and the electrostatic properties of the powder. Foam towprepping may be an attractive alternative to conventional prepregging processes. For example, the impregnation of fiber bundles with polymers in the melt state is successful for some polymers (if the melt viscosity is not too high), but the high melting temperature of many thermoplastics often causes melt prepregging to push the limits of current processing technologies.

At room temperature, polymer is also deposited on carbon fiber by pulling a tow through a dip tank containing a solution or slurry. The tow typically moves through a series of roller bars that act to spread the tow and enhance fiber wetting and resin pick-up. Unfortunately, liquid must then be removed to leave only the resin coating the fibers. The disadvantage of solution or slurry coating is that it takes a significant amount of time to remove the residual liquid from the tow, particularly for solution coating where often times high-boiling solvents (for example, DMAc or NMP) must be used to dissolve the polymer. In addition, solvent-recovery units must be used to meet environmental standards.

As a result of the inherent difficulties associated with melt and solution/slurry prepregging, a greater emphasis has been placed recently on dry powder coating. These powder-coating techniques typically involve pulling a tow through a fluidized bed of polymer powder and relying on the tow to capture the particles with [1, 2] or without [3-6] the aid of electrostatic deposition. The major problem associated with the powder-coating process is that it is difficult to control the amount of polymer deposited on the fiber. The system must be carefully monitored to achieve the desired level of resin pick-up. In addition, dry powder coating does not work well when the polymer is difficult to fluidize if it possesses a static charge and/or a broad particle-size distribution.

This research was performed to develop a novel process for prepregging using an aqueous foam as a carrier medium to deposit polymer powders on carbon fibers. The research emphasizes deposition of high-performance thermoplastic materials for use in the aeronautical and aerospace industries, but the process may be general enough to handle any type of powder.

2. FOAM PROCESS

The ideas for this process stem from work performed in the textile industry where foam-finishing technology is used to apply coatings or finishes to fabric structures [7-12]. A schematic diagram of the proposed foam prepregging process is illustrated in Figure 1. An aqueous foam is composed of a large volume of gas dispersed in a small amount of liquid. The liquid is generally a water-based solution containing a surface-active material (or surfactant) that acts to stabilize the foam. The foam does not necessarily need to be aqueous, although for environmental reasons it would probably be desirable to use an aqueous foam. The polymer powder is slurried in the surfactant solution to a desired solids concentration. The slurry is then combined with air at regulated flow rates to control the volume fraction of gas (also referred to as foam quality). As shown in Figure 1, the slurry and air streams enter a mixing head designed specifically to shear the mixture and generate foam by dispersing the gas in the liquid. The polymer powder is contained in the liquid films and Plateau borders surrounding the gas pockets [13], and the size of the bubbles is controlled by the rotation rate of the mixing head [14]. The foam is then layered onto a spread tow, with the thickness of the layer governed by the height of the exit opening in the reservoir depicted in Figure 1. This technique has the advantages of being relatively simple while maintaining control of the amount of powder that is deposited. The foam-laden tow is then pulled through ovens to collapse the foam and to fuse the polymer to the carbon fibers. The heat from the ovens causes the gas bubbles to expand and burst, and simultaneously vaporizes the small amount of liquid. To promote the deposition of the powder within the tow, it is necessary to spread the tow prior to foam application. Spreading can be achieved using an air-drag technique currently used in conjunction with the powder coating of carbon fibers using a fluidized bed [3-6].

One long-term objective of this research is to be able to use the resin-impregnated tow to fabricate fabric preforms. The towpreg, depending on its flexural rigidity, can be woven into two- or three-dimensional structures that can then be molded into composite parts. Since the resin is built into the preform, this process has a significant advantage over resin transfer molding where, in many cases, the high melt viscosity of the polymer often limits the impregnation of woven materials. The other long-term goal we would like to pursue involves extending this technique to produce flexible prepreg tape. The prepreg would ultimately be handled by tape-laying machines to form multi-ply layups for use in aerospace and aeronautical applications.

Foam prepregging overcomes certain problems associated with dry powder coating. First, since the resin is carried in a surfactant solution, the electrostatic properties and the particle-size distribution of the powder are unimportant. Second, the amount of resin deposited on the moving tow can be easily controlled. Since an aqueous foam has an apparent viscosity that is higher than the individual gas or liquid phases, it behaves much like a continuum

fluid and can be transported from place to place almost as easily as a single-phase liquid. This allows the foam to be applied directly onto the moving tow, and a simple mass balance dictates the level of resin pick-up. The foam process should be relatively simple to control, and it should be possible to continuously produce towpreg or, perhaps more importantly, be implemented into a multi-tow tape line.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The polymer used in this study was the thermoplastic polyimide LaRC-TPI 1500 "high flow" (Mitsui Toatsu Chemicals, Inc., Tokyo, lot 2941) with an average particle diameter of about 23 microns as determined by a Shimadzu particle-size analyzer (Shimadzu Scientific Instruments, Inc., Columbia, MD, model SALD-1100) using laser diffraction. Dynamic scanning calorimetry indicated that the polymer had a melt temperature of about 300°C on initial heating. Surfactant solutions were prepared using Triton X-100, a nonionic surfactant from Rohm and Haas. The polymer was deposited on either unsized 12k AS4 from Hercules or on unsized 3k T-300 carbon fiber obtained from Amoco. The foam was collapsed and the powder melted to the fiber using two Thermolyne tubular furnaces (Barnstead/Thermolyne Corp., Dubuque, IA, Model F21125) in series, each set at approximately 500°C. The temperature setting is a nominal value since there is a radial and an axial temperature distribution within each oven. The tow speed was constant at 2 cm/s and each oven was about 33 cm long yielding a total residence time in the heating step of about 30 seconds, which was sufficient to evaporate the liquid and fuse the powder to the fiber. The resin content in the powder-coated towpreg was evaluated by comparing the weight of a coated sample to that of uncoated fiber of equal length. Photomicrographs were taken with an Hitachi Model S-510 scanning electron microscope (SEM).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Foam Stability

A critical issue in the foam towpregging process is the foam stability. Ideally, the foam should be stable enough to be transported from the foam generator to the tow, but not too stable so as to make it difficult to collapse. It is desirable to use as little surfactant as possible to minimize adsorption at the solid/liquid interface, but a sufficient amount is required to produce a relatively stable foam in the presence of particles [15, 16].

In this study, the stability of foam in the presence of powder was investigated using a mechanical foam generating unit (Oakes Corp., Islip, NY, Model 2MH1A) with a set of intermeshing blades to disperse the gas into the slurry. The slurry was delivered to the dispersing head with a Masterflex pump (Cole-Parmer, Chicago, IL) and the gas flow was regulated using a rotameter. The characteristics of the foam generated with this system

depended on several process variables. The quality (or volume fraction of gas) of the foam depended on the gas and slurry flow rates, while the bubble size was controlled by the rotation speed of the mixing head that dispersed the gas in the slurry.

The foam stability was screened at a slurry flow rate of 17.5 ml/min, a rotation speed of 350 rpm, and a 20 percent w/w slurry in aqueous surfactant solutions of various concentrations. The foams that were generated were collected and weighed in beakers of known volume. The foam quality was then calculated from the measured weight of the foam (which is essentially the weight of the slurry), the predetermined slurry density, and the beaker volume. The object of this study was to reduce the surfactant concentration until a stable foamed slurry could no longer be generated. Figure 2 presents the results of the foam stability study. First note that the results for surfactant concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 1 percent by weight are nearly superimposable, with the foam quality increasing with an increased gas flow rate. However, for a surfactant concentration of 0.1 percent (the solid curve in Figure 2), a stable foam could not be generated for gas flow rates greater than 500 ml/min, simply because there was not enough surfactant present to stabilize all gas/liquid interfaces in the presence of polymer powder. Therefore, to achieve a foam quality greater than 95 percent, a surfactant concentration of 0.25 percent was determined to be the lower limit using a slurry flow rate of 17.5 ml/min, a mixing speed of 350 rpm, and a slurry concentration of 20 percent powder by weight. When no powder was present, a 0.1 percent surfactant solution could be used to generate stable foams with qualities of 96 to 98 percent. But when 20 percent powder was added, stable foams could not be generated at higher gas flow rates, demonstrating the effect of particle addition on foam stability.

4.2 Foam Towpreg Experiments

Preliminary experiments were performed on the NASA Langley powder-coating line. The fiber used was unsized 12k AS4. The foam was applied to the top surface of the spread carbon fiber tow from tubing connected to the output of the foam generator. The initial experiments were performed using a 2 percent aqueous surfactant solution and a low gas flow rate, resulting in a stable foam with a quality of about 95 percent. One tubular oven was used which was heated to a temperature of approximately 600°C. When the foam was applied to the moving tow, the high liquid content caused the relatively heavy foam to slide to the lower surface of the tow, where it frequently fell or was swept from the fiber. Foam that did pass through the single oven was usually collapsed, but the tow was still moist with water that had not evaporated and the powder was not fused to the fiber. These experiments indicated that (1) the foam quality should be increased to make the foam lighter in weight, (2) the surfactant concentration should be reduced to decrease the stability of the foam, and (3) two tubular ovens in series should be used to promote water/surfactant removal and polymer melting.

Using the information gained from the foam stability study, a new set of experiments was performed using a 0.25 percent Triton X-100 solution and a gas flow rate sufficient to achieve a foam quality of at least 97 percent. The slurry flow rate was 17.5 ml/min, the gas flow rate was 570 ml/min, the rotation speed was 350 rpm, and the slurry content was 20 percent by weight LaRC-TPI 1500 high flow powder. The temperature in the central portion of both tubular ovens was fixed at 530°C. Towpreg was produced successfully by applying the foam to the tow from the foam-generator tubing. Water seemed to be removed completely and the polymer was fused to the fiber. An SEM photograph of the foam towpreg with approximately 25 percent resin is shown in Figure 3. The extent of fiber-fiber fusion was nonuniform, and the larger regions of melted polymer contained holes, presumably where water vapor escaped.

Research on the foam process continued at Clemson University by applying foam from a reservoir as depicted in Figure 1. Foam is forced out of the reservoir through a gap of specified thickness to apply a uniform layer of foam to the tow to achieve a uniform and controlled resin content. The carbon fiber used in these experiments was unsized 3k T-300 from Amoco. In addition to the different fiber used, the other difference between these experiments and those performed at NASA Langley was the use of a 0.5 percent Triton X-100 solution (at NASA 0.25 percent was used). The foam process was operated continuously to generate powder-coated tow with an average fiber volume fraction of 58 percent. Towpreg samples were weighed immediately after they were formed and then weighed again one day later. No weight difference was noted, indicating that all of the water had been removed in the heating step. The tow appeared to be covered uniformly with powder, and there was little powder loss during handling.

The foam stability experiments described previously in Section 4.1 were performed to determine the lowest concentration of surfactant that could be used yet still maintain a stable foam in the presence of powders. Even if the surfactant concentration is minimized, it is possible that a fraction of the surfactant adsorbs on the polymer particles [17] and the carbon filaments. A TGA scan was performed on Triton X-100 to determine the temperature at which the surfactant would be removed. As shown in Figure 4, the Triton X-100 is nearly completely removed at about 350°C. Since the temperature of the two Thermolyne ovens is fixed at approximately 500°C and since the surfactant prefers the gas/liquid interface (rather than the liquid/solid interface), it is likely that a large fraction of the surfactant is removed in the heating step. However, surfactant adsorption will be studied in the future by slurrying powders in surfactant solutions of various concentration, stirring the slurries to achieve adsorption/desorption equilibrium, and then centrifuging the slurries. Surface tension and ultraviolet/visible spectroscopy studies will be performed on the decanted liquid phase to determine the amount of surfactant depletion in the solution, which can be attributed to surfactant adsorption on polymer powders. Similar studies can be done with chopped fiber.

4.3 Composite Properties

The flexural properties of a graphite reinforced composite have been obtained from powder-coated prepreg using an aqueous foam to apply the polymer powder. LaRC-TPI 1500 high flow powder was dispersed in a 2 percent aqueous Triton X-100 solution to a concentration of 20 percent w/w powder. The graphite reinforcement was a uni-weave fabric, stitched together every 6.35 mm with glass filaments, and was heated at 316°C for 30 minutes to remove an epoxy sizing. A layer of foam approximately 15 mm thick was applied to one side of the uni-weave fabric, which was stretched between two metal bars for support. The foam/graphite assembly was placed in an oven and heated to 350°C and held for 30 minutes, during which time the foam collapsed and the powder fused to the fiber. The prepreg was then cut, stacked in a matched-metal mold, and compression molded to form a laminate. The compression molding was performed at 2.07 MPa (300 psi) pressure with an ultimate cure temperature of 371°C held for one hour. The composite was virtually void free as determined by ultrasonic scanning and had a resin content of 32 percent by weight. The composite exhibited a 0° flex strength of 1525 ± 124 MPa (221 ± 18 ksi) and a flex modulus of 90 GPa (13 Msi). Considering the fiber waviness in the uni-weave, these results compared favorably with flex properties of LaRC-TPI 1500 high flow composites fabricated using a neutral-buoyancy melt/pultrusion technique [18].

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

A process has been developed in which an aqueous foam is used as a carrier medium to apply polymer powder to carbon fiber continuously. This process is meant to be an alternative to dry-powder processes when the polymer is difficult to fluidize. The powder is slurried in a surfactant solution that is then foamed by dispersing air in the slurry. The foam is applied from a reservoir to a moving carbon fiber tow, and the foam is collapsed and the polymer melted to the fiber in a series of tubular ovens. Powder-coated tow with an average fiber volume fraction of 58 percent was fabricated successfully. The advantage of this process is that, compared to other powder-coating processes, it is easier to regulate the amount of resin deposited on the carbon fiber.

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Figure 1 Experimental apparatus for foam towpregging.

Figure 2 Effect of gas flow rate on the foam quality at various surfactant concentrations in the presence of polymer powder. A stable foam cannot be generated above a gas flow rate of 500 ml/min for an aqueous solution concentration of 0.1 percent Triton X-100 (solid curve). All other results are nearly superimposable.

Figure 3 SEM photograph of foam towpreg. The holes in the larger polymer regions were created by escaping water vapor during heat treatment in the tubular oven.

Figure 4 TGA thermograph of Triton X-100. A large portion of the weight loss occurs between 250°C and 350°C.